

ID-1372

**IDENTIFICATION OF THE ORTHOTROPIC STIFFNESSES
OF COMPOSITES WITH THE VIRTUAL FIELDS METHOD:
PROCEDURE FOR AUTOMATIC DETERMINATION OF
THE VIRTUAL FIELDS**

Evelyne Toussaint¹, Michel Grédiac¹ and Fabrice Pierron²

¹ *LERMES, Université Blaise Pascal, 24, avenue des Landais, BP 206, 63174 Aubière Cedex,
France*

² *LMPF, Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Arts et Métiers, rue Saint-Dominique, BP 508, 51006
Châlons-en-Champagne, France*

SUMMARY: The aim of this work is to present a method allowing the direct measurement of orthotropic stiffnesses of composites from heterogeneous stress/strain fields provided that the whole strain field in one part of the specimen to be tested is known. The method is based on a particular use of the principle of virtual work with special virtual fields that provide a direct relationship between each unknown parameter, the strain field and the applied loading. Some examples of parameter identifications illustrate the approach.

KEYWORDS : Identification, Heterogeneous Stress Field, Testing, Virtual Fields Method

INTRODUCTION

The design of composite structures requires the determination of the mechanical characteristics of the materials to be used. Such characteristics are difficult to determine in the case of composite materials for the main following reasons:

- the number of independent parameters to be determined is important because of the anisotropy and the heterogeneity. Hence several tests must be performed to measure them. For instance, even within the framework of linear elasticity, the number of independent parameters which completely characterize a thin anisotropic plate is important in the general case: twelve instead of the two well-known coefficients of isotropic plates (Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio);
- these coefficients are direction dependent as well as often variable from one point of the structure to the other. They also depend on the manufacturing process that is used. This tends to increase the number of tests to be performed;
- the anisotropy gives rise to particular effects that sometimes disturb the results provided by

usual tests, especially when off-axis tests are performed. In this case, the shear coupling induces heterogeneous stress/strain fields and correction factors or special devices must be used to obtain proper results [1].

These features clearly show that the design of suitable testing procedures is essential for a better knowledge, and therefore a better use of composite materials. A possible way for improving the usual testing procedures is to consider mechanical configurations giving rise to heterogeneous strain/stress fields. The heterogeneity of the strain field is presently no more a drawback but becomes an advantage since several mechanical parameters are involved in those fields. As a result, one can expect to determine the unknown mechanical parameters involved in the field if a suitable processing of the strain field is available.

Several procedures have been presented in the literature for extracting the mechanical parameters from heterogeneous stress/strain fields. Most of them are based on mixed experimental/numerical strategies, in which a cost-function based on the difference between measured and computed strain components, displacements or natural frequencies is minimized with respect to the parameters to be determined [2]. A numerical tool like the finite element method is therefore necessary to identify the parameters. The main drawback of such approaches is mainly the fact that they are iterative and that the boundary conditions must be properly modeled. Another approach called the Virtual Fields Method has been proposed by the present authors. The aim is here to propose an important improvement of the method: the automatic detection of the virtual fields. The procedure is presented in the first part of the paper. It is then compared to the finite element method and some numerical simulations of the procedure illustrate the accuracy and the stability of the approach.

THE VIRTUAL FIELDS METHOD

The test coupon is an unnotched Iosipescu specimen (see Figure 1). The state of stress in the central part of the specimen is heterogeneous. One can therefore expect to extract the mechanical parameters that influence the stress/strain. Assuming that the whole actual strain field in the central part of the specimen is measured, for instance with a suitable optical method, we can expect to extract the unknown parameters provided that an efficient numerical method is available. Indeed, no beam closed-form solution is available for the actual stress/strain field because of the too short distance between the grips. Most of the identification methods proposed in the literature are based on iterative finite element calculations for which the mechanical parameters are adjusted in such a way that the measured data match the calculated one. The idea is here to use the Virtual Fields Method which is based on the principle of virtual work which writes

$$-\int_V \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}^* dV + \int_{\partial V} T_i u_i^* dS = 0 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 : Tested specimen

where σ is the actual stress field, ε^* , u^* are the virtual strain and displacement fields and T is the surface density of external forces on the boundary of the specimen which resulting force is P in the y -direction. This equation is very general since it is valid for any kinematically admissible virtual field. Let us consider that the material is orthotropic, we have

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_s \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{xx} & Q_{xy} & 0 \\ Q_{xy} & Q_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{ss} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_s \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where the rule of contracted indices is used: x holds for xx , y for yy and s for xy , with $\varepsilon_s = 2\varepsilon_{xy}$.

In this case, the global equilibrium (1) writes

$$Q_{xx} e \int_S \varepsilon_x \varepsilon_x^* dS + Q_{yy} e \int_S \varepsilon_y \varepsilon_y^* dS + Q_{xy} e \int_S (\varepsilon_y \varepsilon_x^* + \varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y^*) dS + Q_{ss} e \int_S \varepsilon_s \varepsilon_s^* dS = -Pu_y^*(L) \quad (3)$$

where e is the thickness of the specimen and $L=30\text{mm}$ the length of the central part. This equation where the material parameters are unknown is linear and valid for any virtual field. The basic idea of the Virtual Fields Method [3] is to write Equation (3) with as many different virtual fields as there are unknown parameters to be identified, four in the present case. A linear system is then obtained that provides the unknown parameters. Until now, these virtual fields were obtained intuitively, using a trial-and-error procedure. However, this method was not systematic and one had no guarantee to obtain the “best” set of virtual fields in terms of accuracy and stability of the results. In this work, the objective is to present a procedure which generates automatically the best virtual fields.

DIRECT IDENTIFICATION WITH SPECIAL VIRTUAL FIELDS

The idea here is to constrain some of the coefficients of the unknowns in Equation (3) to be equal to 0 except one which will be set to 1. For instance, if the goal is to extract one of the stiffnesses, say Q_{xx} , one will search among the infinity of virtual fields the one (or those)

denoted ε'^* , u'^* which verifies (verify) the following

$$\oint_S \varepsilon_x \varepsilon_x^* dS = 1, \oint_S \varepsilon_y \varepsilon_y^* dS = 0, \oint_S (\varepsilon_y \varepsilon_x^* + \varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y^*) dS = 0, \oint_S \varepsilon_s \varepsilon_s^* dS = 0 \quad (4)$$

Such virtual fields are called henceforth « special virtual fields ». With such fields, Equation (3) reduces to

$$Q_{xx} = -Pu_y^* (L) \quad (5)$$

where $u_y^* (L)$ is the vertical virtual displacement of the right-hand grip obtained with the special virtual field u^* . Indeed, only the actual field in the central part of the specimen will be processed. The reason is that any parasitic effect in the grips will be avoided. This is one of the advantages of the Virtual Fields Method compared to the methods based on iterative finite elements calculations for which the actual loading distribution must be entered precisely in the model. Consequently, the virtual field is solid-rigid like in both grips. The left-hand side grip does not virtually move (the virtual field is kinematically admissible). The right-hand side grip will only move vertically to compute in practice only the virtual work of the resulting vertical forces.

One can observe in Equation (5) that the unknown parameter is directly equal to the virtual work developed by the applied loading. In terms of units, this result is correct since the « 1 » and « 0 » in Equations (4) are given in m^3 . Hence, Q_{xx} is given in Nm/m^3 , that is Pa. By changing the location of the « 1 » in Equation (4), it is clear that the four unknowns will be obtained successively. Hence, an important objective is to find a procedure to obtain these special virtual fields automatically.

PROCEDURE FOR AUTOMATIC GENERATION OF THE SPECIAL VIRTUAL FIELDS

Let us now examine how to obtain these special virtual fields u^* . Only the headlines of the method are presently given for the sake of simplicity. Full details can be found in Ref [4].

In this central part, it is proposed to write the virtual displacement as a polynomial

$$u_x^* = x(x-L) \sum_{i=0}^m \sum_{j=0}^n A_{ij} x^i y^j, \quad u_y^* = x \sum_{k=0}^p \sum_{l=0}^q B_{kl} x^k y^l \quad (6)$$

It can be easily checked that the virtual displacement is zero in the left-hand side boundary with the grip. Hence, the virtual field is continuous between the central part and the left-hand side

grip. As explained above, the virtual displacement of the right-hand grip must be solid-rigid like and vertical only. It must also be continuous at the boundary between the central part and the right-hand side grip. It can be easily checked that q additional relations between the B_{kl} 's must be also verified

$$\sum_{k=0}^p B_{kl} = 0, \forall l = 1, q \quad (7)$$

The problem is now to find the A_{ij} 's and the B_{kl} 's that will completely define the special virtual fields and therefore the unknown material parameters.

First, the maximum degree of the monomials in Equation (6) are fixed to obtain a maximum degree of 3 for both displacement components: $m=1, n=3, p=2, q=3$. Hence, 20 coefficients A_{ij} or B_{kl} are to be determined. The virtual strain components are obtained by differentiation of Equation (6) and introduced in the four equations (4), leading to four linear equations between the A_{ij} 's or B_{kl} 's. $q=3$ additional equations result from the additional conditions (7). 7 linear equations between the 20 unknown coefficients are therefore available. To solve such a system, all the possible 7×7 determinants that can be extracted from the 7×20 matrix of the system are computed. The cases for which this determinant is greater than a given value are considered. In these cases, the coefficients corresponding to the $20-7=13$ columns that are not in the determinant are fixed a priori and the linear 7×7 system is inverted. Thus one obtains the 20 coefficients that completely define the special virtual fields. Since 13 coefficients are fixed arbitrarily, one can deduce that the special virtual fields are not unique when they exist. This feature is very important: it means that an infinity of different estimates will be found for each of the four material parameter.

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Introduction

The aim of the present work is to show the accuracy and the stability of the present method. Hence the data processed herein are simulated strain components provided by a finite element calculation carried out with the ANSYS package. The program also provides the global force applied at the moving grip. The central part of the specimen is meshed with 2400 height-noded elements. The identification program has been developed with the Matlab package. The threshold value of the determinant is chosen in such a way that only some tens of special virtual fields are obtained for each stiffness. Hence some tens of different values are obtained for each stiffness, allowing to analyze the results in terms of average, standard deviation and search of optimal virtual fields that provide the lower sensitivity to noisy input data. Note finally that the

13 A_{ij} or B_{kl} coefficients for which the stiffness is fixed a priori are set to zero. Indeed, some preliminary calculations have shown that such zero coefficients lead to more stable values of the stiffnesses when noisy data are processed.

Results

A glass/epoxy woven material that exhibits a very low anisotropy is used for this first simulation. The fibers are aligned with the x-axis of the specimen (see Figure 1). The four reference values of the stiffnesses are reported in Table 1. They correspond to the through-thickness properties that have been measured in a thick laminated plate.

	Q_{xx} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{yy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{xy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{ss} GPa
reference	25.94	10.37	3.11	4.00
identified min	25.96	10.14	3.03	4.00
identified mean	25.97	10.24	3.10	4.00
identified max	26.01	10.27	3.11	4.00

Table 1. Reference and identified stiffnesses, material 1

As can be seen, the identified values are very close to reference ones. The scatter is also very small, showing that all the special virtual fields provide about the same value. It is worth noting that the shear stiffness is obtained exactly. This is certainly due to the fact that the shear stresses are predominant in the central part of the specimen.

Some examples of special virtual fields are reported in Figure 2. Several points are worth noting:

- concerning the fields found for Q_{xx} and Q_{yy} , it is clear that all of them correspond to some small variations about an “average” field. On the other hand, the fields found for Q_{xy} exhibit some important virtual displacements in the central part of the specimen. The virtual fields found for Q_{ss} are very similar;
- it must be emphasized that for each stiffness, the virtual vertical displacement of the right-hand side grip is the same from one field to another. This illustrates the very low scatter of the results provided by the special virtual fields;
- as shown above, the identified stiffnesses are proportional to the vertical virtual

displacement of the right-hand side grip. This order of the magnitudes of the four stiffnesses is visually illustrated with the vertical virtual displacement of the fields from one case to the other: First Q_{xx} , then Q_{yy} , Q_{ss} and Q_{xy} .

a- special virtual fields for Q_{xx}

b- special virtual fields for Q_{yy}

c- special virtual fields for Q_{xy}

d- special virtual fields for Q_{ss}

Fig. 2 : Examples of special virtual fields, material 1.

Influence of the anisotropy

Other sets of reference data corresponding to different types of anisotropy have been also considered as input in the programme. The results obtained with a carbon/epoxy unidirectional composite that exhibits a higher anisotropy are reported in Table 2. In this first case, the direction of the fibers is 0 deg., i. e. the fibers are aligned with the x-direction of the setup.

	Q_{xx} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{yy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{xy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{ss} <i>GPa</i>
reference	180.36	10.02	3.01	5.00
identified	181.19	10.02	3.02	5.00

Table 2. Reference and identified stiffnesses, material 2

In this case too, the identified values are very close to the reference ones, showing a very good efficiency of the identification procedure.

Influence of noisy input data

In this type of inverse problem, a keypoint is the stability of the results when noisy data are processed. Two types of perturbations have been investigated. First, a white noise has been added to the strain components considered as input data (i.e. zero mean/random distribution). It has been observed that the identified value were only very slightly affected by such a noise and the results are therefore not reported here.

Another approach consists in adding a constant value to the coordinates of the nodes where the strain components are given by the finite element programme. This error corresponds in practice to an unavoidable shift of the camera that would capture the actual displacement/strain field onto the central part of the specimen. The identification programme has been run with a simultaneous horizontal and vertical shift p equal to $p=4\%$ of the length of the central part in the x-direction and 4% of the width in the y-direction. The constitutive material is the above material 1. The first method for finding the “best” stiffnesses was to compute the average of the values provided by the set of special virtual fields. The results are reported in Table 3, line 2 .

	Q_{xx} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{yy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{xy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{ss} GPa
reference	25.94	10.37	3.11	4.00
method 1	22.13	13.31	2.65	3.74

	-14.3 %	28.3%	-14.8%	-6.5%
method 2	25.71	11.38	3.08	4.00
	-0.5%	9.7%	-1%	0%

Table 3. Reference and identified stiffnesses, material 1, $p=4\%$.

As can be seen, the quality of the results is lower than in the above cases, with a sensitivity to the shift that depends on the stiffnesses. The optimized virtual fields corresponding to a shift $p=4\%$ are plotted in Figure 3.

A second approach has been also developed. Since an important number of identified stiffnesses is available (one for each virtual field), the idea is to find the field which is the less sensitive to a shift. To find it, the identified stiffnesses are collected for each value of the shift and the field which corresponds to the lowest variation of these stiffnesses is considered as the « optimized virtual field ». The stiffnesses found with this second method are reported in Table 3, line 3. It can be seen that the stiffnesses found are much closer to the reference values than with the first method.

The corresponding optimized special virtual fields are plotted in Figure 3.

a- optimized special virtual field for Q_{xx}

b- optimized special virtual field for Q_{yy}

c- optimized special virtual fields for Q_{xy}

d- optimized special virtual fields for Q_{ss}

Fig. 3 : Examples of special virtual fields, material 1.

In order to assess the influence of anisotropy, the procedure has been applied with the second material. The results are reported in Table 4 for various values of the shift p . As can be seen, the stiffnesses obtained are very stable and remain close to the reference values, even at $p=4\%$. It can be observed that the sensitivity of the stiffnesses to a shift depends on the stiffness. It is in fact probably due to the influence of each stiffness to the actual stress/strain field.

The optimized special virtual fields obtained at $p=4\%$ are plotted in Figure 4. As above, it clearly appears that Q_{xx} is the highest value since the virtual vertical displacement of the right-hand side grip is the highest of the four fields in Figure 4.

p %	Q_{xx} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{yy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{xy} <i>GPa</i>	Q_{ss} <i>GPa</i>
reference	180.36	10.02	3.01	5.00
0	181.19 <i>-0.09%</i>	10.02 <i>0.5%</i>	3.02 <i>0.03%</i>	5.00 <i>0%</i>
1	181.08 <i>0.36%</i>	10.07 <i>0.5%</i>	3.02 <i>0.03%</i>	5.00 <i>0%</i>
2	180.70 <i>-0.36%</i>	10.23 <i>2.1%</i>	3.00 <i>-0.03%</i>	5.00 <i>0%</i>
3	180.21	10.50	3.00	5.00

	-0.63%	4.8%	-0.03%	0%
4	179.45	10.88	2.99	5.00
	-1.05%	8.58%	-0.07%	0%

Table 4. Identified stiffnesses for different values of the shift p , material 2.

CONCLUSION

The main aspects of the virtual fields method used for the determination of the elastic constants of an anisotropic material from heterogeneous stress/strain fields are described in the paper. It is shown that special virtual fields allow the direct identification of the unknowns. Some examples illustrate the accuracy and the stability of the identified constants for two types of materials. This approach can also be used for the determination of parameters governing a nonlinear response of the constitutive material [4].

a- optimized special virtual field for Q_{xx}

b- optimized special virtual field for Q_{yy}

c- optimized special virtual fields for Q_{xy}

d- optimized special virtual fields for Q_{ss}

Fig. 4 : Examples of special virtual fields, material 2.

REFERENCES

1. F. Pierron and E. Alloba and Y. Surrel and A. Vautrin, Whole-field assessment of the effects of boundary conditions on the strain field in off-axis tensile testing of unidirectional composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, 1998, Vol. 58, No 12.
2. M. Tanaka and H. D. Bui, *Inverse Problems in Engineering Mechanics*, Springer Verlag, 1992.
3. M. Grédiac, Principe des travaux virtuels et identification/Principle of virtual Work and identification, *Compte-Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences*, II/309, 1--5, 1989.
4. M. Grédiac, E. Toussaint, F. Pierron, Applying the virtual fields method with special virtual fields for the direct determination of material parameters from whole field data, Technical Report LERMES 12-2000, Blaise Pascal University, Clermont-Ferrand, France, 2000.